

Leaching of Basic Cations in Some Soils of Central Southeastern Nigeria

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Abstract: Leaching of some soils of southeastern Nigeria was investigated using free survey method. Soil samples were collected from soil profiles based on horizon and analysed using routine analytical tools. Data generated were subjected to descriptive statistics. Field studies indicated sandiness of soil, weak to strong structural grades, friable soil consistence, imperfect to poor drainage (Shale-derived) and well drained epipedons and endopedons (Alluvium derived). Basic cations were generally low but increased with soil depth. Values of basic cations and total exchangeable bases were higher in endopedons compared to their values at the epipedon. Calcium-Magnesium ratios were less than 3:1, which is sometimes considered as critical limit for good yield. Calcium-Magnesium ratios ranged from 2.07-5.04 in shale, 2.52-2.92 in Alluvium, 2.20-3.38 in oil spilled soil and 1.83-3.10 in unspilled soil.

Keywords: Basicity, fertility, leaching, lithology, translocation

Introduction

Leaching is one of the prominent pedogenic processes of loss in tropical soils. It involves vertical movement of basic cation of exchangeable calcium (Ca^{2+}), exchangeable magnesium (Mg^{2+}), exchangeable potassium (K^+) and exchangeable sodium (Na^+) from epipedal horizon of the soilsphere towards endopedon. Leaching process is heightened in these soils due to high rainfall amount, intensity and duration amidst potentially vulnerable and fragile soils characterized by sandiness, poor aggregation, low resistance to rain drop impact and impoverished soil organic matter (SOM) content. These soils have for long time be subjected to intense above ground loss of vegetal resources due to increasing demographic pressure and conflictive land use.

Most Arable and tree crop farmers who stick tenaciously to old ways of cultivating crops progressively experience poor yield as a consequence of leaching process. This is very applicable to all soil group in Nigeria particularly in the southeastern agroecology. Farmlands in soils developed over Bende-Ameki Formation (Shale), Nsukka formation (Upper Coal Measure), Mamu formation (Lower Coal Measure), Benin formation (Coastal Plain Sands), Ajali formation (Falsebedded Sandstone) and alluvial deposits have variously shown signs

and symptom of soil degradation through leaching.

Leaching of basic cations, some which are secondary macronutrient contributes substantially to soil fertility status of humid tropical soils especially in rainforest belt of southeastern farmlands. Calcium-Magnesium ratio less than 3:1 inhibits uptake of available phosphorus and reduced availability of exchangeable calcium while the approximate optimum for most field crops is 3:1 to 4:1 (Landon, 1991). Possible implication of these is nutrient imbalance which negatively influence the basic cation uptake and other nutrient especially macronutrient availability, especially phosphorus and unhealthy acidification of most tropical soils leading to yield decline in farmers' field. Onweremadu (2022) reported that these soils become problematic and exhibit various forms of deficiencies ranging from yellowing between nerve ends (magnesium deficiency), burnt colouration of leaf edges of older leaves (Potassium deficiency), browning, greying and white spot on leaves (manganese deficiency), brown top of arable crops (calcium deficiency) and reddish purple colours on leaves and stem (Phosphorus deficiency). Soil with sandy texture are observed to be excessively leached resulting to low basic ion contents of epipedon (surface soils) beyond the reach

of shallow rooted arable crops. In addition to leaching of basic cations from the surface soils, Agbede 2011 reported that maize yield of 5.0 tonnes per hectare leads to removal of 75kg, 25kg and 20kg of potassium, calcium and magnesium, respectively from soils.

Given the above and the need to increase crop yield to content with the increasing population of southeastern region of Nigeria, it become necessary to investigate the status of basic cation in some location of central southeastern Nigeria. The major objective of this study was to assess the distribution and status of basic cation in soil profile of selected sites in Southeastern Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated the fertility of these location using calcium –magnesium ratio as criterion.

Materials and Method

The study was conducted in Central Southeastern Nigeria located between Latitude $4^{\circ} 30'$ and $8^{\circ} 30'$ N and Longitude $6^{\circ} 20'$ and $8^{\circ} 20'$ E. The lithologic materials consist of shales, sandstones, coal measures, sand and alluvial deposits. The geomorphology of the area consists of low lying lands, depressions and plain with few gentle to undulating slopes. Southeastern agroecology lies within the humid tropics with annual rainfall of about 1800mm to 2500mm and annual temperature range of 27 to 31°C . Relative humidity is generally

high and exceed 80% during wet seasons. The Southwest and Northeast Trade winds govern the rainfall and dryness characteristics of the region. Soils are sandy and generally well drained but imperfectly drained at most of the water courses. The hydrology of the area is governed by rivers, lakes and their tributaries. The vegetation of the sites is predominantly rainforest with the density reduced by anthropogenic activity especially farming, deforestation, industrialization, mining and human settlement. Small holder farming is the major socio-economic activity of the area and food crops are chief crops of the farmers' field. Processing and cottage industries exist while crude oil exploitation are found in certain locations of the agroecology.

Field Studies

A free survey was conducted in which choice of sites were based on features of great pedological implication relevant to leaching dynamics. Soil profiles were dug, described and sampled according to FAO (2006) guidelines. Soil Profiles were georeferenced using Handheld Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver (Garmin Ltd, Kansas USA).

Macro morphological properties were observed and recorded using appropriate field tools. Soil samples were air dried and

passed through 2mm sieve, preparatory for laboratory analyses.

Laboratory Studies

Exchangeable basic cations were extracted using 1N Ammonium acetate. Determination of exchangeable calcium and magnesium was performed using ethylene diamine tetracetic acid titration and exchangeable potassium and sodium were analysed by flame photometry (Thomson 1982). Calcium-Magnesium ratio was obtained by calculation.

Statistical Analyses

Both primary and secondary data were analysed using appropriate statistical tools ranging from mean, standard error in differences in means, coefficient of variation and ranked using Wilding et al., (1985).

Results and Discussion

Macromorphology: Two modal soil profiles developed over different parent materials: Shale (Bende) and Alluvium (Egbema) indicated distinct horizonation (Table 1).

Soils were deep exceeding 100cm (0-146cm for Bende and 0-135cm for Egbema), implying potentials of soils materials to move from surface horizons (epipedon) to subsurface horizon (endopedons).

Soil colour under moist soil condition exhibit shades of dark brown, gray to yellowish red with distinct red mottles (Bende: Shale) while it showed dark brown, brown, reddish brown to red without mottles in soils derived from Alluvium (Egbema). Darker colour at the epipedon suggested greater interaction of soil matrix with vegetal materials, which decrease in the endopedon.

Sandy clay loam and sandy clay dominated the texture of Bende (shale) while loamy sand to sandy loam characterized soils texture of Egbema (Alluvium). Sandy texture permits easy translocation by water resulting in dissolution and movement of basic cations from epipedon to endopedon especially in areas situated in the rainy humid tropic region. Sand-sized particles dominate soil texture of soil groups in the Central Southeastern Nigeria. Sandiness of these soils particularly influence packing of primary particles resulting in various forms of spaces and void that might promote leaching of basic cations down the soil profile.

Grade of soil structure, indicative of its strength, ranged from moderate to strong in Bende while weak to moderate in Egbema soils. Fine, medium and coarse (Bende) and fine to medium (Egbema) class were recorded. Subangular structured type dominated in Bende soils unlike Egbema

soil characterized with mix of granular type (epipedon) and subangular type of structure (endopedon). These structural attribute suggest that conventional tillage practices which is common in this agroecology might promote soil structural degradation and enhance leaching of basic cations particularly in Egbema soils. The situation might be heightened with friable and very friable consistency at the epipedons of soils for Bende and Egbema, respectively.

Soils are well drained, imperfectly drained to poorly drained at Bende while at Egbema, the soils are well drained (Table 1) suggesting possible removal of basic cations which could be more pronounce in Egbema soils with good drainage.

Roots were more abundant and distributed in horizon of Egbema, implying of the possibility of these roots to create translocatory channels that promote water movement in the soilsphere.

Table 2 shows the distribution of basic cations down the soil profiles developed on Shale (Bende) and Alluvium (Egbema). Irrespective of parent material, exchangeable basic cations increased with depth leading to higher values of exchangeable calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium at the deepest horizons. Highest values of total exchangeable bases were found at deepest

horizon in both soil groups. With the exception of epipedon of soils derived from Shale (Bende), Calcium-Magnesium ratio were below critical limit of 3:1 suggested by Landon (1991). The result indicated pronounce leaching in these soils, which invariably has led to low Calcium-Magnesium ratios in the soils.

Scholars have attributed excessive leaching in the agroecology to differences in lithological origin of soils (Onweremadu, 2007), land use type (Ahukaemere, 2015) and heavy rainfall (Wenibo, 2022).Asadu (2022) reported that leaching of these basic cations tended to be temporal and gradual, resulting to acidification of soils of Southeastern Nigeria.

Exploration and exploitation of crude oil resulting in accidental discharges of the resource on soils did not differ in leaching nature of these soils. Both spilled and unspilled sites had the basic cation concentration at the deepest horizon. However, mean values of the basic cations were higher in unspilled sites when compared with spilled soils.

Table 1: Macro Morphology of Soils Developed Over Two Parent Materials

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Colour (moist)	Mottles	Texture	Structure			Consistence (moist)	Drainage	Roots	Inclusions	Boundary	
					Grade	Class	Type					D	T
Bende (Shale) 5° 33' 09'' N, 7° 38' 03' E'													
A	0-8	DB(10YR3/3)	-	Sandy Clay Loam	2	f	sbk	friable	WD	mf/m	-	c	s
AB	8-24	B(10YR4/3)	-	Sandy Clay Loam	2	f	sbk	friable	ID	mf	-	g	w
Bt ₁	24-55	G(7.5YR4/1)	Red(2.5YR4/6)	Sandy Clay	2	m	sbk	firm	PD	ff	-	g	w
Bt ₂	55-110	G(7.5 YR5/1)	Red(2.5YR4/8)	Sandy Clay	3	Co	sbk	firm	PD	ff	-	g	s
Bt ₃	110-146	YR(5YR4/6)	-	Sandy Clay	3	Co	sbk	firm	PD	r	-	-	-
Egbema (Alluvium) 5° 28' 31.840'' N, 6° 47' 6.802'' E													
A	0-13	DB(10YR3/3)	-	Loamy Sand	1	vf	gr	very friable	WD	cf/m	-	c	w
AB	13-22	B(10YR5/3)	-	Loamy Sand	1	f	gr	very friable	WD	mf/m	Krotovina	c	w
BA	22-25	B(7.5YR4/3)	-	Sandy Loam	1	f	sbk	friable	WD	mf/m	-	c	w
Bt ₁	25-80	RB(5YR4/3)	-	Sandy Loam	2	m	sbk	slightly firm	WD	ff/m	termite relic	g	s
Bt ₂	80-153	R(2.5YR4/8)	-	Sandy Loam	2	m	sbk	slightly firm	WD	vff	-	-	-

Horizonation: A=Surface master horizon, AB= transitional horizon of master horizons A and B with A dominant, B= subsurface master horizon B, BA = transitional horizon of master horizon B and A with B dominant, Bt =master horizon B indicating Argillation (clay formation)

Soil Colour: DB= dark brown, B=brown, G=gray, RB= reddish brown, YR= yellowish red, R=red.

Soil Structure: Grade; 1=weak, 2=moderate, 3=strong

Class; vf= very fine, f=fine, m=medium, Co=coarse

Type; gr= granular, sbk = subangular blocky

Roots: mf/m=many fine and medium,cf/m= common fine and medium, ff=few fine, vff= very few fine, r=rare.

Boundary: D=Distinctiveness; c=clear, g= gradual

T=Topography; s=smooth, w=w

Field Survey, 2023

Table 2: Leaching in Soils Developed Over Two Parent Materials

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	TEB	Ca/Mg	
		<----- ----->						
		cmol/Kg						
Bende (Shale) 5° 33' 09" N, 7° 38' 03' E'								
A	0-8	2.42	0.98	0.31	0.02	3.73	5.04	
AB	8-24	2.60	1.13	0.33	0.02	4.08	2.30	
Bt ₁	24-55	2.66	1.20	0.41	0.03	4.30	2.21	
Bt ₂	55-110	2.70	1.27	0.45	0.05	4.47	2.12	
Bt ₃	110-146	2.82	1.36	0.46	0.09	4.73	2.07	
Egbema (Alluvium) 5° 28' 31.840" N, 6° 47' 6.802" E								
A	0-13	1.86	0.70	0.11	0.03	2.70	2.58	
AB	13-22	1.90	0.72	0.15	0.03	2.80	2.63	
BA	22-25	2.02	0.80	1.17	0.03	3.20	2.52	
Bt ₁	25-80	2.43	0.83	0.19	0.04	3.49	2.92	
Bt ₂	80-153	2.46	0.92	0.20	0.05	3.63	2.67	

Ca = calcium, Mg = magnesium, K= potassium, Na = sodium, TEB = total exchangeable bases
Field Survey, 2023

Table 3: Leaching and Crude Oil Spillage in Southeast Nigeria

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Ca ⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	TEB	ECEC	B sat (%)	Ca/Mg
Egbema (Spilled)									
A	0-19	0.90	0.41	0.51	0.10	1.92	4.29	33.00	2.20
E	19-23	0.71	0.21	0.40	0.06	1.38	2.89	32.00	3.38
Bt ₁	23-60	0.83	0.34	0.42	0.10	1.69	3.71	37.00	2.44
Bt ₂	60-118	1.10	0.38	0.43	0.13	2.04	4.09	37.00	2.89
Bt ₃	118-212	1.30	0.39	0.48	0.14	2.31	5.40	29.00	3.33
Mean		0.97	0.35	0.45	0.11	1.88	4.68	33.60	2.85
SD		0.23	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.35	0.91	3.00	0.53
CV (%)		24.00	23.00	10.00	30.00	21.75	22.00	10.00	19.00
Egbema (Unspilled)									
A	0-15	1.21	0.66	0.90	0.30	3.07	5.70	54.00	1.83
AB	15-54	1.10	0.45	0.60	0.15	2.30	4.60	50.00	2.44
Bt ₁	54-90	0.96	0.41	0.52	0.14	2.03	4.13	49.00	2.34
Bt ₂	90-160	1.16	0.40	0.60	0.17	2.33	4.09	57.00	2.90
Bt ₃	160-210	1.30	0.42	0.48	0.60	2.80	5.21	53.00	3.10
Mean		1.15	0.47	0.62	0.27	2.51	4.75	52.60	2.52
SD		0.10	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.40	0.70	3.00	0.50
CV (%)		11.0	23.00	27.00	72.00	33.25	15.00	6.00	20.00

Ca²⁺ = exchangeable calcium, Mg²⁺ = exchangeable magnesium, K⁺ = exchangeable potassium, Na⁺ = exchangeable sodium, TEB = total exchangeable bases, ECEC = effective cation exchange capacity, B sat = base saturation, Ca/Mg = calcium magnesium – ratio
Sule (2023)

Optimum Calcium-Magnesium ratio was recorded at the middle horizon of soils while ratios indicating poor fertility were observed at the epipedons. Higher values of effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation were observed in the unspilled soils

Conclusion

Concentration of basic cations (calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium) were observed at endopedons of soils of Central Southeastern Nigeria irrespective of lithologic origin. There were low values of Calcium-Magnesium ratio, often used as an index of soil fertility in farmers' fields.

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